
Pilot report

ARCF

QUESTION 1

Taking into consideration the Transformational Modules, what concrete steps did the team take to answer the TMs?

Can you please make one case study specific in which you feel the pilot excelled?

For the ARCF Pilot team the networking part was extremely important. It allowed all of us in the Pilot team to reach out from the academic loneliness we were facing every day in our institutions and find like-minded people who have similar curiosities and research interests. The additional resources we received were also used largely for networking and capacity building activities - during our short pilot we organised two large international conferences and one international seminar, with hundreds of participants in total, creating a vibrant network that just keeps growing and expanding even after the pilot has ended. Two Special Editions of peer reviewed journals also are a way to expand the network. We are excited by how quickly the network grew and by how enthusiastically it was received by researchers from all around the world and we could not have done it without the RIT funding.

QUESTION 2

Any challenge or barrier to reporting, in particular in these topics, core to the dynamic clusters:

- interinstitutional collaboration

Challenges were mostly simple and bureaucratic. How the workload of each school is calculated is different and it creates situations whereby some researchers have to do the Pilot research from their free time.

- interdisciplinary collaboration

The ARCF project itself was aimed for interdisciplinary collaboration, so it is something we enjoyed and excelled at. Our events brought together neuroscientists, filmmakers, teachers and film scholars and

as it was the original aim of our Pilot we believe that it is a good case study of how to build interdisciplinary bridges.

- inter-human collaboration

We were delighted by how well our team worked. We believe that much of it is because it was a small pilot project, no-one was burdened with excess bureaucracy, unnecessary meetings or such, thus the collaboration flourished throughout the project. We might have wanted to possibly create something more together, but it will be the task of our follow-up activities, as what we envisioned, we also finished.

QUESTION 3

What management /collaboration tool did the Pilot Team use? How did the team use it, for what main purpose, and how did you evaluate it?

Mostly we used the Teams, and by and large the chat function of the Teams or meeting function of the Teams. For our conferences (the online part) we used Zoom for presenters and Youtube streaming for viewers. For presentations (including some video essays) we used Power Point. For joint writing we used Google Docs.

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